

Recycle And Reuse of Plastic Waste to Manufacture Plastic Fly Ash Sand Brick and Compare It with Normal Clay Brick

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Abstract— Plastic waste which is boosting day by day becomes horror and in turn pollutes the terrain, especially in high mountain villages where no scrap collection system exists. The use of plastic has grown broadly in recent times each over the world. Still plastic is non- biodegradable; it causes pollution and produce difficulties in managing indeed for a fat nation. The purpose of this study was to probe the terrain-friendly implicit use of plastic and demonstrate mileage of plastic sand bricks as essential structural rudiments, replacing standard complexion slipup.

We are girdled by plastics. Important of our furniture, vesture, electronics, and food packaging are made from it. Over the onetime decades, natural material used in manufacturing comparable as paper, glass, and cotton, has been replaced by plastic. We know that this ubiquitous use of plastics has led to extreme plastic pollution of our terrain. Still, plastics are not just an environmental issue. Hence, these waste plastics are to be effectively employed. Low- viscosity polyethylene bags are gutted and added with beach at particular probabilities to attain high strength bricks that own thermal and sound sequestration parcels to control pollution and to reduce the overall cost of construction; this is one of the stylish ways to avoid the accumulation of plastic waste which is an on- degradable contaminant. This alternately saves the volume of beach/ complexion that has to be taken down from the precious swash beds mines. The plastic waste is naturally available in fat volume and hence the cost factor comes down.

Keywords— Plastic production, Plastic waste, Recycling methods, Sustainable reuse, Environmental impact, Construction materials

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I. INTRODUCTION

Plastic, a product of petrochemicals introduced in 1907, has revolutionized various industries due to its unique properties. Comprised of synthetic or semi-synthetic organic compounds with high molecular mass, it can be shaped into solid forms through molding processes. Its production involves polymerizing or polycondensing natural materials like cellulose, coal, natural gas, salt, crude oil, minerals, and plants. Plastic stands out for its versatility, weight, durability, flexibility, variety, and affordability, surpassing materials like wood, natural fibers, rubber, and paper in many aspects.

Despite its numerous benefits, the widespread use of plastics has led to significant environmental challenges. Common plastics like Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE) and High Density Polyethylene (HDPL), widely employed in packaging, pose serious threats due to their slow decomposition rates, often taking over a century to break down. Improper disposal leads to clogged waterways, landfills, and harm to aquatic and terrestrial wildlife.

Managing plastic waste presents a daunting task, even for affluent nations. Effective solid waste management systems and recycling initiatives are crucial steps towards mitigating this issue. Innovations such as incorporating plastic waste into brick production offer promising solutions. Plastic bricks, created by reusing low-density polyethylene, not only reduce waste but also lower brick production costs. Compared to traditional clay bricks, plastic bricks boast a smooth finish, crack resistance, low water absorption, and eliminate issues like efflorescence. Furthermore, they contribute to sustainable development and environmental conservation by reducing reliance on resource-intensive materials like clay or concrete, which generate greenhouse emissions during production.

II. MATERIAL USED

A. Plastic

Plastic comprises synthetic or semi-synthetic materials primarily composed of polymers. It is predominantly generated from various plastic products like single-use bottles, disposable plastics, multi-layered packaging, and similar items, contributing to environmental pollution and posing significant threats to human and wildlife habitats. When exposed to sunlight, plastic waste emits methane and

ethylene, potent greenhouse gases, due to its low density. Commonly, there exist seven types of plastics on Earth, including PET (Polyethylene Terephthalate), HDPE (High-Density Polyethylene), LDPE (Low-Density Polyethylene), PVC (Polyvinyl Chloride), PS (Polystyrene), PP (Polypropylene), and other miscellaneous variants.

B. Sand

Sand is a granular material composed of small rock and mineral particles that have undergone coarse fragmentation. It differs from gravel and silt in its particle size, being finer than gravel yet coarser than silt.

There are various methodologies employed by different researchers for utilizing plastic waste in construction materials. Some utilize low-density plastic by cutting it into small pieces and mixing it with a cement-sand-aggregate mixture. Others burn plastic and combine it with materials like iron chips, bitumen, or rice husk. In this study, the approach involves melting plastic and mixing it with sand. Specifically, four types of plastic are used: Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE), Polystyrene (PS), High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE), and Polyphenylene Ether (PPE). These plastics are collected and cleaned, removing impurities by washing and drying them naturally. The plastics are then shredded or cut into small pieces to increase their surface area, aiding in melting. The plastic, fly ash, and sand are mixed in various proportions by weight, such as 1:1:1.5, 0.8:1:1, and 1:1:0.75.

III. MATERIAL COLLECTION

Plastic waste, including items like bottles, food packages, polybags, and bottle caps, can be gathered from various sources such as canteen garbage, households, local dumping sites, and hospitals. Sand can be procured from nearby suppliers.

A. Batching of Material

Batching involves weighing and measuring the materials. Plastic waste is checked for moisture content and dried if necessary. Medium sand, suitable for plastic brick production, is obtained through sieving.

B. Proportion of Plastic and Sand:

Different ratios of sand, plastic, and fly ash are considered for making plastic bricks, such as 1:1:1.5, 0.8:1:1, and 1:1:0.75 by weight.

C. Development of Brick Mould:

Metallic moulds are used instead of wooden ones to facilitate easy compaction of the plastic and sand mixture without wear and tear. Metallic moulds offer smoother surfaces, resulting in bricks with sharp edges and smooth surfaces. The mould size is typically 10x10x10cm.

D. Procedure for Casting of Brick:

Procedure for Casting of Brick:

Melting: Plastic pieces are melted in a container, ensuring they are fully dried to prevent excessive smoke.

Mixing: Sand is added to the container while the melted plastic's temperature remains between 180°C to 220°C. The mixture is continuously stirred for proper blending.

Moulding: The inside surface of the mould is oiled to ease brick removal. The prepared mixture is poured into the mould and compacted using a rod.

In this study, various physical and mechanical tests were performed on both plastic and traditional bricks. These tests included evaluations for soundness, efflorescence, hardness, impact resistance, and overall structural integrity. Additionally, compression strength tests were conducted on both types of bricks.

IV. EXPERIMENT ON PLASTIC BRICK

To assess the performance of plastic brick walls, specifically those made of High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE), walls were constructed using HDPE bricks measuring 500 × 110 × 500 mm. These plastic brick walls were compared to conventional brick walls of the same dimensions, following the guidelines outlined in IS 1905:1987. The objective was to analyze differences in crack patterns and load-bearing capacities between the two types of walls.

Given the superior compressive strength of HDPE bricks compared to Polypropylene (PP) bricks, the study focused particularly on HDPE bricks. Fire resistance tests were carried out on both plastic and conventional brick walls, adhering to the standards specified in Table 1 of Part 4 of SP 7: Group 1 (2005) of the National Building Code. Detailed soundness and hardness tests were conducted as described in Figure 1 of the study.

A. Compressive strength test

The universal testing machine, with a capacity of 1000 kN, was used to test the HDPE, PP, and conventional brick samples. Results showed that HDPE bricks could withstand an ultimate load of 191.35 kN with a displacement of 18.40 mm, while PP bricks held up to 171.35 kN at a displacement of 15.30 mm. Conventional bricks exhibited an ultimate load of 178.95 kN with a displacement of 13.50 mm.

Using computerized UTM, Load vs Displacement graphs were generated, illustrating the performance of the brick specimens. Analysis of failure patterns revealed that plastic bricks developed vertical cracks in the tension zone, leading to edge splitting, whereas conventional bricks were completely crushed.

Comparing compressive strengths, HDPE bricks outperformed PP bricks, recording 11.19 N/mm² and 10.02 N/mm² respectively. Additionally, HDPE bricks exhibited significantly higher compressive strength than conventional bricks, which measured 10.50 N/mm², as depicted in the provided figure 1.

B. Compressive strength test on plastic brick and conventional brick wall

A plastic brick wall underwent testing using a computerized Universal Testing Machine (UTM) with a maximum capacity of 1000 kN. Initially, the wall remained stationary under a load of 16 kN. However, as the load increased, the wall eventually reached its ultimate load-bearing capacity of 197.5 kN, causing a displacement of 27.50 mm. This progression is depicted in the accompanying figure.

According to IS 1905:1987 standards, a correction factor is applied to the experimental compressive strength value, accounting for the height-to-thickness (h/t) ratio of the wall. With a calculated h/t ratio of 4.54 and employing interpolation, the correction factor for the brickwork specimen is determined to be 0.97. Consequently, the corrected or normalized compressive strength of the wall is calculated.

Furthermore, the normalized masonry efficiency is derived by comparing the normalized or corrected compressive strength with the strength of individual bricks. The failure of the plastic brick wall involved the crushing of bricks, spalling of mortar cover, and debonding between bricks. Additionally, shear failure was observed at a 45° angle within the wall, as depicted in the provided figure.

Parameters	Plastic brick wall	Conventional brick wall
Dimensions: b × t × h (mm)	500 × 110 × 500 mm	500 × 110 × 500 mm
Weight (kg/m)	47.53	104.353
Density (kg/m ³)	1728.363	3794.654
Compressive strength (N/mm ²)	3.59	2.79

The water absorption test is conducted to assess the ability of bricks to absorb water, which should not exceed 20% of their weight for optimal strength. Initially, the bricks are dried in an oven at a temperature between 105°F to 115°F until they achieve a consistent weight, which is denoted as W1. After cooling, the dried bricks are weighed again.

Next, the dried bricks are submerged in clean water at room temperature (around 27°C) for a period of 24 hours. Once removed from the water, any excess moisture on the surface of the bricks is gently wiped off using a moist towel before they are weighed again, denoted as W2.

The water absorption capacity of the bricks is then calculated using the formula

$$W = \frac{w_1 - w_2}{w_2} \times 100$$

SR.NO	Sample	Dry Weight in kg	Wet Weight (w2) in kg	W%
1	Brick1	1.358	1.365	0.515
2	Brick2	1.946	1.964	0.924
3	Brick3	1.857	1.864	0.376

V. RESULT ANALYSIS

Water absorption of the given brick is 0.840 which is < 1%.

A. Efflorescence Test

The efflorescence test involves submerging one end of the brick vertically in water, ensuring that the submerged portion is at least 25 mm. The setup is then placed in a well-ventilated warm room with a temperature range of 20° to 30°C until all the water has evaporated. Once the bricks appear dry, a comparable amount of distilled water is added and allowed to evaporate. Following this, the bricks are examined for efflorescence, characterized by white areas or dots on the surface.

Efflorescence is categorized as follows:

- Nil: No salt deposition or white areas are observed.
- Slight: A thin layer of salt covers less than 10% of the

surface area.

c. Moderate: Heavier salt deposition, covering up to 50% of the surface area.

d. Heavy: Salt deposition exceeding 50% of the surface area without flaking or powdering.

e. Serious: Salt deposition exceeding 50% with flaking or powdering, and tending to increase with repeated soaking.

B. Hardness Test:

In the hardness test, the surface of the brick is scratched using a fingernail or a sharp implement. If no scratch marks are visible, the brick is considered hard.

C. Soundness Test:

For the soundness test, two bricks are gently struck against each other to determine if a clear ringing sound is produced. If the brick remains intact and generates a clear ringing sound, it is deemed to be sufficiently sound.

CONCLUSION

The research and experimentation aimed to address the environmental challenge posed by plastic waste by repurposing discarded plastic materials into High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE) and Polypropylene (PP) plastic bricks. These innovative bricks offer numerous advantages over traditional ones. Notably, they are crafted entirely from recycled plastic waste without the need for water in their production process.

HDPE and PP bricks display remarkably low water absorption rates of 0.75% and 0.37% respectively, making them particularly suitable for construction projects where water infiltration is a concern. Moreover, the use of these plastic bricks significantly reduces the weight in structures by as much as 55% compared to conventional bricks.

In terms of strength, HDPE plastic bricks outperform conventional bricks with a 14.6% higher compressive strength. Their load-bearing capacity is also noteworthy, as demonstrated by HDPE brick walls supporting an ultimate load of 197.5 kN compared to 153.95 kN for conventional brick walls of the same size. While initial bond strength between plastic bricks and mortar may be lacking, this can be improved by incorporating design features such as frogs or rough textures on the brick surfaces.

The lightweight, strong, and non-absorbent nature of plastic bricks makes them an excellent choice for masonry wall construction, particularly in civil infrastructure projects and tall buildings. By adopting plastic bricks, the construction industry can significantly reduce its environmental impact while simultaneously enhancing construction efficiency.

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